

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MODERN ARABIC AND CLASSICAL ARABIC

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Abstract

In this article we wrote, we tried to identify the differences between modern Arabic and classical Arabic. In our study, we first talk about the history of the Arabic language, some linguistic features, common types, which type is more common and how to learn it easily. In addition, in the article we will talk about the features of both the modern Arabic language and the classical Arabic language and learn which one is more advanced in the spread of the Arabic language. We will talk about classical Arabic and different Arabic dialects in Arab societies, their features and their role in education. Next, Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), the different Arabic dialects in Arab societies, and its role in education will be discussed. As a result of many years of research, the various stages of development and progress of the Arabic language, the emergence of the religion of Islam and the revelation of the Holy Quran in Arabic are stated as the main events in the spread of Islam.

Keywords: Arabic Language, History of the Arabic language, Modern Standard Arabic, Classical Arabic, Spoken Arabic, Arabic dialects.

INTRODUCTION

One of the languages considered a member of the Semitic language is Arabic. It was created by combining different languages such as European-Asian languages (Hebrew, Ethiopian, etc.). This language first appeared in the world as Arabic in VII century BC. The full formation of the Arabic language is related to the spread of Islam after the death of Muhammad prophet. Arabic is known as the most widely used language among the Semitic languages. There are more than 330 languages in the Semitic language group, and the Arabic language has managed to maintain its place among these languages. The founding of the Islamic Arab empire occurred in the second half of the seventh century. After that, this empire expanded from Spain to Iran and contributed to such a great administration in a short time. Arabic, known as the sacred language of the Quran, began to spread rapidly in large areas as a sacred language.

Its development in this form was considered an impetus for its spread from the Arabian Peninsula to distant places [5].

According to the information provided by the Central Intelligence Agency in 2008, it is the language of Muslims and more than 1 billion people in the world, and it is a language that millions of people learn with pleasure. Arabic is the sixth most spoken language in the world and one of the six official languages. According to the UN, most Arabic speakers are Christians and some are Jews, but people think that only Muslims know Arabic. Babayev Javid underlines important details about the integration of Arabic into Azerbaijani as other Muslim countries: “As we know, terms used in a language source from religion, culture and history. The words present in a language cover a special layer. For example, when we take part in a funeral or burial ceremony in Azerbaijan, we hear the mullah speak in the Arabic language. It does not mean that the Arabic language has already integrated into our language in this

field. Because this language is only understood by mullahs and the people who know Arabic. If most people understood and used those Arabic words, it could be considered as an integration. Some commonly-integrated Arabic words covering religious terms predominate not only in funeral ceremonies in Azerbaijan but also in all Muslim countries. The religious words such as namaz, mullah, akhund, inshallah, mashallah and others have already been accepted as internationalized words which are used in all Muslim countries” [6]. Well, this is not the case, top-notch organizations have confirmed in their own information.

In world-level indicators, Arabs are more recognized as traders and immigrants. Through trade and migration, Arabic became widespread for communication in regions such as Iraq and the Nile. In other cities, the Arabic language was seen as a powerful means of communication in Egypt, Syria and Palestine. It expanded throughout the Islamic world thanks to familiarity with the Arabic language in such regions. After the spread of Islam, the Arabic language began to develop further. It was clear that Arabic was the dominant language among North African and Middle Eastern countries [8].

Arabic, an Eastern-derived language of the Eurasian family and a member of the Semitic group, is believed to have spread from the Levant, the Fertile Crescent, and the Arabian Peninsula. As a result of the research, they divided the development of the Arabic language into 5 stages. The first stage is ancient Arabic (or proto-Arabic), the second stage is early Arabic, the third stage is classical Arabic, the fourth stage is Middle Arabic, and the fifth stage is modern Arabic [7].

If we look at the history of the Arabic language, Arabic belongs to the European-Asian language group, which includes more than 300 languages. Arabic and Hebrew are considered 2 rare examples of living languages. It is recorded that the first find of the Arabic language was found in a book dating back to IV century in the Syrian desert. The lack of written information,

they say, delays the study of the nature of the Arabic language.

There are very few written records from III to VII centuries, one of which is epigraphic. Found in north-western and central Arabia, this form of information is short rock inscriptions and graffiti [7].

This finding, a literary treasure of the Arabic language, was not systematically recorded in writing until 2000. No documentation has been produced regarding this finding [7]. The Arabic language is found in poems that were created orally and passed down from year to year before the time of the Prophet Muhammad. It is said that the Arabic writing system originates from the combination of Syriac and Nabataean scripts. Both of these languages started from the Aramaic language. In the early Islamic era, the Arabic language was mentioned in two main sources: the Holy Quran and the poems in Islam [8]. The two sources we have were considered pillars for the standardization and codification of the Arabic language. These two sources have an important place in the development of the Arabic language.

The spread of the Islamic state, which developed from the 8th to the 12th centuries, resulted in the transition of the Arabic language into the language of international civilization, culture, scientific writing and research, and the spread of diplomacy and administration [7]. Scientific works accepted by high state authorities and references to the field of science in Europe are written in Arabic. Arabic was considered a leading year for the Middle Ages. European heads of state were sending their children to regions where the Arabic language was widespread to learn different advanced sciences.

Therefore, the Arabic language was considered equal to the level of the English language, which has taken over our world today. Most instructional materials are in English around the globe as it is an international language [2]. Arabic is also an international language. Scholars have many works written in Arabic. These scholars include Al-Bayruti (1048), Ibn Sina (1037), Al-Tabari (923) and others. For this reason, a number of scholars, including Arabs, non-Arabs and even Christians, have encouraged the development of the Arabic language, especially in intellectual terms. Arabic language literature and different branches of science had reached their golden age.

Unlike the scientific level, the Arabic language had several dialects. For example, the Meccan dialect was considered a modern language due to its high level. To this day, the Quraysh dialect is used as a variant of the standard Arabic language. This dialect (قریش قبیلة - job tribe) was considered a high-level dialect. The reason for its superiority over other Arabic dialects is that the rulers of the Arabian Peninsula live among tribes and its strategic location is also considered a meeting point for trade and goods caravans. It should be noted that the city of Mecca is considered the homeland of the Quraysh. For this reason, Arabs coming to Mecca to complete their prayers was considered the most important factor in the spread and development of trade and the Arabic language. It is believed that this dialect comes from the Holy Quran belonging to the Quraysh tribe under the name Muhammad dialect.

If we agree with the predictions of grammarians, the first standardization phase of the Arabic language dates back to VIII century. The records we have show that the first codification of the Arabic language was discovered by early Arabic grammarians. This period dates back to VIII century. It is stated in the notes that the language of the Quran was chosen among the dialects during this coding stage. When people spoke "Lahnul Amah", the rules of the Arabic language began to be violated. The reason for this is that illiterate people cannot speak Arabic correctly. To prevent this, Arab grammarians created rules and laws that defined the "correct" ways to speak and speak Arabic. It was a process designed to preserve the beauty and purity of Arabic, considered the language of the Holy Quran, the symbol of Islam, from destruction [8].

In XX century, the Arabic language entered a new phase with the emergence of a new genre. This phase developed during globalization, internationalization and the use of many political, technological, medical and technical terms by Arabs with the outside world. Due to the requirements of modernity, Arabic is accepted as the official language of twenty-four countries in the world. It is one of the six official languages of the UN. These countries include Eritrea and Chad, as well as the twenty-two regions of the Arab Emirates. 50 percent of the countries that use the Arabic language are in Africa. These regions include Libya, Morocco, Mauritania, Somalia, Sudan, Algeria, Comoros, Djibouti, Egypt, Eritrea, Chad and Tunisia. The other 50 percent is in Asia. These countries include Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, United Arab Emirates, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Oman, Palestine, Qatar, Syria and Yemen [7].

Alphabet of the Arabic language

Let's look at the alphabet of the Arabic language. Although the Arabic alphabet contains consonants and various vowels, the Arabic alphabet consists of only 28 letters. Arabic grammar is slightly different. Since there are no short vowels, written words consist only of consonants and long vowels. The most distinctive feature of the Arabic alphabet is that it is written and read from right to left. In a different feature, I should point out that the six Arabic letters (ا, ذ, ر, ز, و) have two shapes, while the others have four shapes. A distinctive feature is that no capital letters are used in the Arabic alphabet, as capital letters are not used in Arabic. Quotation marks or parentheses are used to distinguish between common and proper nouns. If we look at its grammar, we see that Arabic belongs to the phyletic language group. If we look at the explanation of the phyletic group, we can see that new words are formed through radical phyloction. It has been determined that words in noun groups such as nouns, adjectives and numbers only have simple, possessive and active forms.

Dialects new Arabic has five dialects that should be considered an independent language. The dialects used are very different from each other. Because there are so many differences, it may sometimes be necessary to consider a new form of Arabic. The reason for such a difference is the rapid spread of the Arabic language, the ethnic groups in the regions where it spread, etc.

The main dialects of the Arabic language are as follows. Egyptian dialect, Maghreb dialect, Mesopotamian dialect, Gulf dialect, Shami dialect.

The Egyptian dialect is also known as the Masri dialect. It is a dialect belonging to the Hami-Sami family, affiliated with the Semitic branch. It comes from the Nile Delta outside the capital Cairo. Almost the entire Arab world understands this dialect perfectly. According to estimates, fifty-two million people in Egypt use this dialect, and twenty-four million people use it as a second language. This dialect has no official status. Classical Arabic is considered the official language of the Egyptian state.

The Maghreb dialect is considered a dialect spoken by seventy-five million people in Morocco, Algeria, Sahara, Tunisia and Libya. Arabs living in the Middle East do not understand this dialect very well. During the French period, it was taught as a different language in schools.

The Mesopotamian dialect is divided into two. Iraqi dialect and Northern Mesopotamian dialect.

Iraqi dialect is the dialect used in the Iraq region. This dialect itself is divided into 3 parts. Baghdad, Mosul and Basra Dialects. Twenty-nine million people in Iraq, eastern Syria and western Iran use this dialect.

The Northern Mesopotamian dialect is used in the northern part of Baghdad, the far east of Syria, and some regions in eastern Turkey. Approximately seven million people speak this dialect.

Another name for the Shami dialect is **Eastern dialect**. Thirty-five million people are said to use this dialect. It is said that the Shami dialect is divided into six different dialects.

The Gulf dialect is spoken by four million people in Iraq, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Oman, Yemen, Qatar and Bahrain [10].

Modern Arabic

According to calculations, the Arabic language began to spread rapidly in the modern era, which coincided with the late XVIII century. Although the Arabic language suffered the most at the hands of the Ottoman state, it experienced a brief development under the rule of the Ottoman state in XX century. [3]. One of the biggest steps taken against Arabic was Muhammad Ali's replacement of Turkish with Arabic, the official language of government in Egypt. Thanks to this step, the modern Arabic language began to develop again as a means of production. Muhammad Ali's reign is considered the beginning of the Arab Nahdaor renaissance [4].

Thanks to this step, Arab scientists and writers are considered to have reached a new stage. They saw that the Arabic language had difficulty expressing technological terms and modern social and cultural ideas. Due to this problem, terms began to be derived from classical Arabic for modern Arabic. More European terms were used. The development of the modern Arabic language occurred rapidly in the 1930s and 1940s [6].

Let's look at some interesting facts about the modern Arabic language. First of all, I would like to point out this fact that caught my attention during my research. In other words, there are more than 100 words expressing the word camel in the Arabic language.

The words "cebir", "kireç", "sahara", "şeker" used in English are borrowed from modern Arabic. A distinctive feature of the modern Arabic language is that letters are written in different ways depending on their use at the beginning, middle and end of sentences. Modern Arabic is mostly spoken in Egypt, United Arab Emirates, Iraq, Algeria, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Syria, Tanzania, Yemen, Chad, Comoros, Djibouti, Eritrea, Tunisia. The number of modern Arabic speakers is 200,000,000.

Classical Arabic

The most important period for the development of the Arabic language is the period when the Classical Arabic language emerged. The earliest evidence for the creation of the classical Arabic language was found in pre-Islamic poetry of VIII century AD. Therefore, it was preserved through active oral transmission until it was recorded in writing in VIII century AD [9]. During the times when the classical Arabic language began to emerge, writing poetry was considered a very elegant and popular official profession, even a tribal tradition. There was a common opinion among Arab and Western linguists that this movement took place in the dialects of the Arabic language in the first stage [1]. The language of the Quran, which is considered the basic spiritual text of Islam, is classical Arabic. Classical Arabic is called Quranic Arabic. Classical Arabic is a well-known Old Northern Arabic language. Classical Arabic is the only surviving language of the Arabic dialect group. Classical Arabic has become a language used for religious purposes rather than a spoken language. Those who want to read the Quran in its original language need to learn classical Arabic perfectly.

Difference between modern Arabic and classical Arabic

One of the main differences between modern Arabic and classical Arabic is the form in which they are presented. While Qur'anic (classical) Arabic is more common in literature and writing, modern Arabic is used more orally, that is, in conversation. Since modern Arabic has its roots in classical Arabic, there is not much difference between them. To quickly learn Arabic as a resource, it is very simple to learn classical Arabic and then switch to modern Arabic. Modern Arabic is a somewhat standardized form of the classical Arabic that is taught to us in schools and appears in official statements, newspapers, etc.

Modern Arabic is useful for conducting professional and academic work. Modern Arabic is currently used all over the world. For example, during a trip to the Middle East or Arabic-speaking Africa, it is possible to see the following.

- Street signs
- Television news programs
- Newspapers
- Books
- University Research
- Store Signs

CONCLUSION

In this research article, we have identified the differences between the modern Arabic language and the classical Arabic language. In our article, we first gave

information about the origin of the Arabic language, its alphabet, grammar, dialect, classical and modern Arabic language. Our main work is to clarify the differences between Classical Arabic and Modern Arabic. We note that the classical Arabic language predated Islam and was used for writing and religious purposes. Modern Arabic language is more common in communication. Why should we learn modern Arabic? Because modern Arabic is used in international collaborations, events and professional work. Modern Arabic is one of the 6 main languages of BTM. When we visit any country in the world, we will find newspapers, street signs, magazines, etc. that will display the modern Arabic language. From this we conclude that if we want to study the Arabic language in the modern age, we need to learn the modern, that is, standard Arabic language.

References

1. Altoma, Salih J: Arapçada Diglossia Problemi: Klasik ve Irak Arapçası üzerine karşılaştırmalı bir çalışma: Harvard University Press. Anis, Ibrahim (2003).
2. Babayev, J. (2021). The role of instructional materials in language learning. *ELMİ XƏBƏRLƏR, Humanitar elmlər seriyası*, 2, 29-35.
3. Brugman, Jan (1984): An introduction to the History of Modern Arabic Literature in Egypt, Brill, Leiden
4. Chejne, Anwar (1969): The Arabic Language: Its role in history. University of Minneapolis Minnesota Press.
5. Holes, Clive (2004): Modern Arabic: structures, functions and varieties. Washington, D.C.: Georgetown University Press. Ibn Khaldun (1967 [1377])
6. Javid Babayev. (2024) A language inside a language. zərbaycan Dillər Universiteti və Naxçıvan Dövlət Universitetinin birgə təşkilatçılığı ilə Ümummilli Lider Heydər Əliyevin anadan olmasının 100 illiyinə həsr olunmuş "Tərcüməşünaslığın müasir problemləri" mövzusunda Respublika elmi konfransı
7. Ryding, Karin C (2005): A Reference Grammar of Modern Standard Arabic.
8. Zahrani M. A. (2020) "Hypothetical and Counterfactual Mood Markers: Hierarchical Placement". *The International Journal of Arabic Linguistics (IJAL)*, 1,2, 6/167-191. Edited by Versteegh, M. Eid, A. Elgibali, M. Woidich, and A. Zaborski.
9. <https://comme-un-pro.fr/az>
10. <https://language.az/10131398.html>